

Working with communities,
advisory groups, policy makers
and partners

Mahidol Oxford Tropical Medicine Research Unit (MORU)
Bioethics and Engagement Department
420/6 Rajvithi Rd., Thung Phaya Thai
Ratchathewi, Bangkok, THAILAND 10400

Email: BEMORU@tropmedres.ac
Twitter/X: @MORUBKK

Public and community engagement and involvement across the MORU Tropical Health Network

The Mahidol Oxford Tropical Medicine Research Unit (MORU) Tropical Health Network conducts clinical research on infectious diseases and maternal and child health across Asia and Africa. MORU's mission is to improve the health and wellbeing of people living in low-resource settings. These people are threatened by inequity in health care, climate change and conflict, and they suffer and die disproportionately from preventable and treatable infections.

MORU has an active community and stakeholder engagement programme coordinated and supported by the Department for Bioethics and Engagement team, led by Professor Phaik Yeong Cheah. We have teams based at MORU Bangkok, at SMRU at the Thai-Myanmar border, the Chiang Rai Clinical Research Unit (CCRU), and Siem Pang Health Centre (Cambodia).

We work to build long-term relationships with local communities and groups underserved by research, to ensure that MORU's research is relevant, ethical, and responsive to their needs. By focusing on the social, cultural, and economic contexts of the communities, we aim to foster trust and meaningful collaboration.

This brochure showcases some of the many engagement projects run by MORU engagement staff and researchers over the years. Our engagement activities are informed by continuous evaluation and social science research. We share our learnings via publications, talks and publicly accessible formats. Selected references, videos and websites are listed at the end.

At the core of MORU's engagement programme is a network of adult and youth advisory groups that provide us with valuable insights and advice on how to conduct our research and health programmes in the most ethical and impactful way.

Our oldest running group is the Tak Province Community Ethics Advisory Board (T-CAB) on the Thai-Myanmar border, established in January 2009. Its members are Karen and Myanmar migrant workers and villagers who share a common interest in serving their community, ensuring access to healthcare, protecting the rights and wellbeing of community members participating in research, and highlighting their community's health needs.

Made up of young people aged 16 to 22, the Siem Pang, Cambodia Youth Advisory Group on Health & Research (YAGHR) gives local youth a platform to have their voices heard in matters relating to their health and health research conducted in the Siem Pang area.

The Siem Pang Youth Advisory group members visit the lab/clinic. Photographer: Nicky Almasy

The Siem Pang Youth Advisory Group on Health & Research. Photographer: Nicky Almasy

Our other advisory groups are the Bangkok-based Health Research and Ethics Interest Group, the Aileen Young Person's Advisory Group in Mae Sot, the Chiang Rai Hilltribe Advisory Group, and the Pakistan Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement Group.

The Aileen Young Person's Advisory Group, Mae Sot. Photographer: Supa-at Asarath

The Bangkok Health Research and Ethics Group (HREIG). Photographer: Supanat Ruangajorn

A meeting of the Mae Sot Young Person's Advisory Group (Y-PAG). Photographer: Supa-at Asarath

Many of our projects use science-arts and participatory methods that support power sharing and mutual learning to work with communities in creative ways.

The Village Drama Against Malaria project travelled as a road show through Cambodia's Stung Treng, Battambang and Pailin provinces from 2016 to 2019. In this innovative project, MORU researchers collaborated with local health authorities and a local drama group to create an

Children on stage portraying mosquitoes that carry the malaria parasite, in the “Village Drama Against Malaria” project. Photographer: Nicky Almasy

art-based programme that engaged rural communities on malaria and malaria research. In total, Village Drama Against Malaria reached 55 rural villages, 2,378 student participants and 43,502 audience members. The project won the University of Oxford Vice Chancellor’s Gold Award for Public Engagement in 2019.

Under the Mask is a 2019 film based on the real testimony of tuberculosis patients (TB) living on the Thai-Myanmar border. It was co-produced by SMRU and Sermpanya Foundation, a Mae Sot based charity organisation that creates and disseminates video and digital media campaigns in collaboration with refugee communities to respond to the needs of refugees, migrant communities, and cross border villagers. The project used a participatory approach to filmmaking, with the director, cast and crew drawn from communities along the Thai-Myanmar border, allowing TB patients to tell their story of life with TB.

Screenshots from the film ‘Under the Mask’

Conducted in 2018-2019, the project *Imagine IN, Express OUT: How I perceive my health?* captured the stories and fears, anxieties and hopes of marginalised populations on the Thai-Myanmar border. The SMRU team, together with Karen and Myanmar artists from the community-based organisation ‘Kick Start Art’, ran drawing activities as art therapy for Myanmar migrant populations of pregnant women and patients with TB and/or HIV, and an art summer camp for migrant youth students. The project concluded with an art exhibition that displayed participants’ artwork at migrant schools in Mae Sot districts.

Participants’ art work from the “Imagine IN, EXPRESS OUT” project

MORU routinely conduct education and engagement on general health, especially in the communities where our clinics and research sites are based.

For example, CCRU led a series of training sessions in remote districts of Chiang Rai province, where scrub typhus is endemic. For this, CCRU partnered with the Social and Preventive Medicine Department, Chiang Rai

A picture drawn by Chiang Rai artist Pisan Kamwang, used for the CCRU scrub typhus training materials

Community health volunteers at Pa Daet Primary Care Unit, Chiang Rai province, participating in a role play training session on scrub typhus. Photographer: Phatharath Thira-preedatapp

Prachanukroh Hospital, and the Primary and Holistic Service Department, Mae Suai Hospital. The sessions engaged community health volunteers and healthcare workers, raising awareness about scrub typhus and its prevention. Additionally, community health volunteers joined by CCRU staff conducted sessions with villagers to observe and compare the effectiveness of different training materials.

We also deliver health education and engagement initiatives in response to the needs of communities.

For example, during the COVID-19 pandemic, we conducted extensive engagement around COVID-19 on the Thai-Myanmar border. A lack of or no access to accurate and reliable information in local languages on COVID-19 vaccine among migrant workers caused high rate of vaccine hesitancy. To ensure that migrant workers on the Thai-Myanmar border had access to correct information, the SMRU public engagement team liaised with community health workers and local key contact persons to identify migrant communities and clusters and plan information campaigns. In 2021, the team delivered 91 information campaign sessions to over 10,000 migrants in five border districts.

Our children and youth engagement projects include advisory groups, co-production initiatives, school workshops and lab visits.

Villagers attending a COVID-19 engagement session. Photographer: Napat Khirikoekkong

Students from Ban Muangkarn School, Chiang Khong district, Chiang Rai province, participating in the KAP-SCHOOL project. Photographer: Phenpisa Khampan

The KAP-SCHOOL project engaged Golden Triangle border primary and secondary school students in Chiang Rai Province in Thailand with the science and prevention of COVID-19. In a series of interactive workshops, the team used a do-it-yourself 3D hologram projector to show a coronavirus model and discuss COVID-19 and vaccines. The students then worked in groups to develop their own educational videos targeting school students and their families and communities, with advice on wearing facemasks and handwashing to prevent COVID-19 transmission.

Our engagement activities centre around our main research themes like malaria, TB, maternal and child health, and antimicrobial resistance (AMR).

The AMR Dialogues project brought together members of the public from different backgrounds and regions in Thailand, NGO representatives, AMR researchers and national policy makers in a series of participatory conversation events. In ‘community conversations’, participants co-created solutions specific to each local context to reduce the AMR burden in Thailand. At the end, the team provided recommendations for the Thailand National Strategic Action Plan on Antimicrobial Resistance (2022-2027).

Participants and facilitators sharing experiences of antimicrobial resistance as part of an ‘AMR Dialogues’ community conversation event. Photographer: Supanat Ruangka-jorn

The landing page of the '[Antibiotic Footprint Calculator](#)' website.

The interactive online *Antibiotic Footprint Calculator* lets users quickly estimate their antibiotic footprint based on their consumption of antibiotics in medicines and food. Users can compare their individual footprint with others in their own country and around the world. The website explains the science behind antimicrobial resistance and gives tips to reduce individual antibiotic consumption. The project was developed in partnership with Greenpeace Thailand and World Animal Protection Thailand.

GroupMappers is a crowdsourcing initiative based in Bangladesh that uses Geographic Information Systems (GIS) to address critical public health issues, allowing the public to get directly involved in conducting research. Initially focused on mapping isolated communities in southeastern Bangladesh, it expanded its scope by integrating activities such as collecting spatial data, analysing disease distribution, and assisting the government with healthcare interventions across the country. GroupMappers works with Bangladesh's Communicable Disease Control division of the Directorate General of Health Services. Comprised of a core team based in Dhaka, and supported by a cohort of volunteers, GroupMappers is funded by donations via the Oxford Development Office and external grants.

GroupMappers volunteers engaging with village heads, to identify and verify community boundaries on satellite imagery

Women health workers learning to digitally collect and upload malaria case data. (Lama, Bandarban 2023)

DPhil students in action at the 3MT competition. Photographer: Supa-at Asarath

We provide regular public engagement training and experience for our researchers and staff to ensure they are supported to get directly involved. In addition to our training programme, our researchers and students can practice their communication skills live on stage.

Every year, PhD and DPhil students from MORU and OUCRU join the Three Minute Thesis (3MT) competition and learn how to explain their research to high school students and members of the public. The 3MT takes place in over 600 universities worldwide every year. It trains and encourages doctoral students to effectively explain their research and its significance in just three minutes, with only one PowerPoint slide. Launched in 2018 at MORU and our Vietnam sister Unit, the Oxford University Clinical Research Unit (OUCRU), the competition is coordinated collaboratively. Finalists from local qualifying rounds present their research to a panel of judges and an audience of high school students. The presenter with the most student votes receives the 'People's Choice' award.

Audience members participating in a science quiz during a break in talks. Photographer: Pint of Science Laos

Audience participation at 'Pint of Science Thailand'. Photographer: Supa-at Asarath

Many MORU researchers have talked about their work for the Pint of Science Festival. Pint of Science is an annual event that brings researchers into cafés, pubs, and other community spaces to share their work in a relaxed and informal setting. In 2017, MORU coordinated the first Pint of Science festival in Asia. In May 2022, Pint of Science Laos launched successfully in Lao PDR. We have also run other public talk events and science cafés in Laos, Cambodia and Thailand.

Selected publications

Motivations and perceptions of community advisory boards in the ethics of medical research: the case of the Thai-Myanmar border. Maung Lwin K, Cheah PY, Cheah PK, *et al.* BMC Med Ethics. 2014 Feb 17;15:12.

A youth advisory group on health and health research in rural Cambodia. Ean, M., Tripura, R., Sothea, P, *et al.* Glob Bioeth. 2024 Jun 7;35(1):2361968

Establishment of a patient and public involvement and engagement group to support clinical trials in Pakistan: Initial lessons learnt. Tolppa T, Hussaini A, Ahmed N, *et al.* Res Involv Engagem. 2024 10, 98.

A hill tribe community advisory board in Northern Thailand: lessons learned one year on. Perrone C, Kanthawang N, Cheah PY. Int J Equity Health. 2024 23, 241.

Drama as a community engagement strategy for malaria in rural Cambodia. Lim R, Tripura R, J Peto T, *et al.* Wellcome Open Res. 2017 Sep 29;2:95.

Community engagement to develop a dialogue-drama on adolescent pregnancy in a marginalised migrant population on the Thailand-Myanmar border: an ethnographic approach to participatory action research. Soe SS, Paw ST, Dah MLT, *et al.* Glob Health Action. 2024 17:1,

Engaging ethnic minority communities through performance and arts: health education in Cambodian forest villages. Callery JJ, Sanann N, Tripura R, *et al.* Int Health. 2021 Feb 24;13(2):188-195.

Under the Mask: A Film on Tuberculosis at the Thai-Myanmar Border. Delmas MV, Soan M, Khirikoekkong N, *et al.* Front Public Health. 2022 Apr 21;10:795503.

Community engagement around scrub typhus in northern Thailand: a pilot project. Perrone C, Kanthawang N, Cheah PY, *et al.* Trans R Soc Trop Med Hyg. 2024 Oct 1; 118(10):666-673

Raising awareness of antimicrobial resistance: development of an ‘antibiotic footprint calculator’. Prapharsavat R, Kittikongnapang R, Smithkittipol C, *et al.* J Antimicrob Chemother. 2023 Jun 1;78(6):1317-1321.

Evaluation of the Pint of Science festival in Thailand. Adhikari B, Hlaing PH, Robinson MT, *et al.* PLoS One. 2019 Jul 18;14(7):e0219983.

Embedding community and public voices in co-created solutions to mitigate antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in Thailand using the ‘Responsive Dialogues’ public engagement framework. Poomchaichote T, Kiatying-Angsulee N, Boonthaworn K, *et al.* Antimicrob Resist Infect Control. 2024 Jul 4;13(1):71.

‘Working relationships’ across difference - a realist review of community engagement with malaria research. Vincent R, Adhikari B, Duddy C, *et al.* Wellcome Open Res. 2022 Jan 13;7:13.

Videos and websites

[T-CAB video](#)

[KAP-SCHOOL](#)

[Cambodia Youth Advisory Group on Health & Research video](#)

[Antibiotic Footprint Calculator](#)

[Village Drama Against Malaria video](#)

[GroupMappers](#)

[Thai AMR Dialogues Brochure](#)

[Under The Mask](#)